

A CRITICAL ANALYSIS ON THE IMPACT OF UTILIZATION OF THE INSTRUCTIONAL RESOURCES ON PEDAGOGY IN PUBLIC SECONDARY SCHOOLS IN KENYA

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Abstract:

The purpose of the study was to critically analyze the impact of utilization of the instructional resources on pedagogy in public secondary schools in Kenya. Most public secondary schools in Kenya are not fully equipped with enough instructional resources. An in-depth analysis was done to bring to light what must be brought forth to equip all schools with essential instructional materials needed during pedagogy. The main intent of the study was to critically analyze the teachers' preparedness to use instructional resources during instruction for the sole benefit of the students in secondary schools in Kenya. To critically analyze how variety of instructional resources impact pedagogy in public secondary schools in Kenya. To critically analyze how simplicity of instructional resources impact pedagogy in public secondary school in Kenya. To critically analyze the impact of the cost of instructional resources on pedagogy in public secondary schools in Kenya. To critically analyze the impact of the adaptability of instructional resources on pedagogy in public secondary schools in Kenya. Moreover the study was meant to generate the impact of inclusiveness of those instructional resources, the cost of the instructional resources and the availability of instructional resources. The study used qualitative research design that was valid when doing a critical analysis. The study came up with recommendations to the government, teachers and the education stakeholders to ensure that teachers get enough training with respect to instructional resources and also acquire variety of resources to enhance pedagogy in public secondary schools in Kenya.

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1. Introduction

According to Fredrick (2009), a resource is anything that is used to make training and teaching easier and facilitate the learning process. Resources help students visualize and think of the concept and science they have encountered in their real life situations and how they either influence it or how it influences them. According to Nelson (2004), “many concepts or ideas are understood visually rather than verbally” on the other hand he has defined teaching as a process of assisting learners to get new knowledge, skills and experience that may be of help and importance to them when they are of age. From the definition of teaching therefore, it can be noted that learning only happens when the learner acquires new knowledge and skills from the teacher, failure to which learning is said not to have occurred.

During the instruction, it is the teacher’s role to carefully select both the teaching resource and the methodology to be used (George, 1985). A qualified and professional teacher can therefore be defined as the one who will choose wisely and selectively the type of instructional resource to use to suit the topic, context and the learning ability of the students. The idea of adopting instructional resource is not a 21st century idea but can be traced to the ancient history of our ancestors. In the holy book, the Bible, Jesus is cited in Luke 22:1 -13 to use illustrations like the bread to signify his body and cup of wine for his blood during his teachings and in the ancient Egypt, Egyptians used illustration drawn from the ground to make pedagogy effective.

2. Statement of the Problem

The Ministries of Education and the education stakeholders have urged teachers to provide not only education to the learners but quality education. The ministry of education through the teachers’ service commission (TSC) has introduced many reforms to the education sector which include the teachers’ appraisal but still making little progress towards quality education and results.

Despite the government allocating more funds towards education and research, the effectiveness of pedagogy in Kenya has not taken roots. Learners in secondary school have not been provided with adequate instructional resources and of different variety to cater for their learning needs. For instance, the report given by the African media and research foundation in 1998 found out that in Taita Taveta most of the schools have dilapidated buildings and there are insufficient books, desks and other

equipment for the pupils. Another follow up study by the Taita Taveta government task force on the factors contributing to the declining secondary school education standards in Taita Taveta county in 2013 gave a report that 7/28 of the schools sampled had no library rooms, 11/28 schools sampled had computer rooms and the rest had none and 17/26 of the schools sampled had no laboratory. This fact has led to low performance among secondary school students in Taita Taveta County and in Kenya as a country since most of the students has average understanding and retention capability and need these facilities to foster their understanding and retention.

3. Purpose of the Study

The purpose of the study was to critically analyze the impact of utilization of instructional resources in public secondary school in Kenya.

4. Objectives of the Study

1. To critically analyze how teachers preparedness to use the instructional resources impact pedagogy in public secondary schools in Kenya.
2. To critically analyze how variety of instructional resources impact pedagogy in public secondary schools in Kenya.
3. To critically analyze how simplicity of the instructional resource impact pedagogy in public secondary school in Kenya
4. To critically analyze the impact of the cost of instructional resource on pedagogy in public secondary schools in Kenya.
5. To critically analyze the impact of the adaptability of instructional resources on pedagogy in public secondary school in Kenya.

5. Research Questions

1. To what extent does the teachers preparedness towards using instructional resources impact pedagogy in public secondary schools in Kenya?
2. What is the effect of variety of instructional resources to pedagogy in public secondary schools in Kenya?
3. To what extent does the simplicity of instructional resource affect pedagogy in public secondary schools in Kenya?
4. What are the effects of the cost of instructional resource on pedagogy in public secondary schools in Kenya?

5. How does adaptability of instructional resource affect pedagogy in public secondary schools in Kenya?

6. Research Methodology

The study was a critical analysis of the impact of instruction resource in pedagogy in secondary schools in Kenya.

The study made use of qualitative method of research which is the most reliable, suitable and valid in coming up with concrete information based on the topic.

The method of study seeks to gather an in-depth reason of human behavior and tries to answer questions like who, what, when and how.

7. Significance of the Study

The study may inform the government and the Ministry of Education of the challenges in the teaching and learning process in Kenya secondary schools in order to allocate funds and facilitation especially to cater for instructional resources and it may also help the Non-Governmental organizations (NGOs) with the challenges facing the Kenyan secondary school classroom in the process of pedagogy in order to provide support through donation and funds.

The study may help public secondary schools students to be exposed to instructional resources as they improve students' academic performance since they improve the retention of knowledge learnt during instruction and it may also help the teachers to know their role as teachers and how they influence teaching. It emphasizes the role of instructional materials as an important ingredient to be used during pedagogy.

8. Critique Literature Review

8.1 A Critical Analysis of Teachers Preparedness to Use Instructional Resources in Public Secondary School in Kenya

Teachers play a key role in implementing major educational changes and policies as prescribed by the government and the educational stakeholders, therefore, it is very essential for teachers to undergo proper training and sensitization to enable efficiency in the use of pedagogical resources. According to the ministry of education science and technology (2005) session paper No1, teachers are cited to be an important resource in the teaching and learning process. Their preparedness enables them to acquire

sufficient subject mastery and pedagogy. The government and the Teacher Service Commission (TSC) should look forward to increasing training facilitation down to the school level to help equip teachers with the basic and requisite skills needed to not only use but also use a variety of pedagogical resources effectively.

Inadequate sensitization and training of the use of the instruction and training of the use of instruction resource leads to the teachers not using modern instructional approaches translating to memorizing and retention of concepts in class.

8.2 A Critical Analysis of the Impact of Variety of Instructional Resources in Pedagogy in Secondary Schools in Kenya

According to (Nelson, 2004, p.359), *“Visual aids add variety and interest”*, variety of instructional resources means having different resources which trigger different interests and senses during pedagogy. Continuous use of a single instructional resource in class, for instance charts, leads to a negative exponential decrease to the learners’ arousal interest toward the resource.

An effective pedagogy is the one where all senses are involved and this includes; sight, smell, touch, taste and hearing. Simultaneous use of different pedagogical resource which trigger different senses enable learners to understand concepts deeply compared to surface memorization where none or one of the resources is used, a situation known as rote learning. George Bishop,(1980) In his book Curriculum

Development argued that it is very important to have insightful learning than rote learning. He continued emphasizing that relationship and principles are more important than facts, he also put more emphasis on application on what is learnt than merely learning

The use of few selected and insufficient instructional resources has created a scene where the Kenyan secondary school students are compelled to memorize content being taught in class which finally translates to difficulty in understanding and low performance.

8.3 A Critical Analysis of the Impact of the Simplicity of the Instructional Resources on Pedagogy in Public Secondary Schools in Kenya

A good quality material is the one that enhances, facilitates and makes training-learning easier with minimal time, energy and expenditure from both the trainer and the trainee (Fredrick, 2009). Training and learning resource should be simple in a way that it will be easy for a student to understand concepts taught with the least effort possible.

According to Jarvis et al., (2000), accommodation cannot take place when a new experience is so radically difficult that it cannot be assimilated into existing schema and

so a new schema is formed. Use of technical and complicated instruction resources in various secondary schools in Kenya has led to students using more effort to understanding the same concepts they would have understood with minimal time and effort and this translates to academic performance. Otherwise, complex instructional resources impair the instructional capability of teachers who have not undergone proper sensitization on the use of such instructional resources.

8.4 A Critical Analysis of the Impact of Adaptability of Instruction Resources on Pedagogy in Secondary Schools in Kenya

Adaptability of an instruction resource is the ability of it remaining relevant and useful in the future generation to come. Secondary schools in Kenya have become victims of possession of many instructional resources ranging from books and much other laboratory equipment which no longer add significance to pedagogy in the current classroom.

Schools and the government put in a lot of effort in terms of finance to purchase instructional resources for instruction in Kenyan secondary schools. This is reflected as a gross loss to the school and the country once the resources can no longer be used during instruction.

Knowledge is dynamic which implies that concepts keep on being added to the domain and some are deleted once they are either outdated or are proved to be wrong. Irrelevant instructional resources, more so textbooks at school, may mislead the students to learn outdated concepts and thus impair their academic performance negatively.

8.5 A Critical Analysis of the Impact of the Cost of Instructional Resources on Pedagogy in Secondary Schools in Kenya

Among other competing and pressing needs in a school set up like making payments to the teaching and non-teaching staff, infrastructural expenditure, electricity and water and many others the school needs to subdivide its financial resource to cater for instructional resource in a school. Bishop, (1985) in his book Curriculum Development argued that too few funds are allocated to educational media in developing countries, he sighted developing countries of having schools with no electricity and some have no floors.

Instructional resources, more so in the science domain are very expensive and only fortunes of the schools in Kenya are able to meet the financial threshold to purchase the resources. It is now common knowledge that for pedagogy to be successful, instructional resources must play part. In this context, the only question we

can ask, is what will become of the schools which cannot meet the cost of the instructional resources? In this context, the cost of instructional resources can be cited to be one chief factor that influences pedagogy in secondary schools in Kenya.

8.6 A Critical Analysis on the Impact of Pedagogy in Public Secondary Schools in Kenya

The question as to what is the right pedagogy to be used in secondary schools is an open ended question which can be discussed without an ultimate answer. Different learners need different pedagogical strategies to achieve efficient learning. Students differ variably according to numerous differences in their background, learning styles and abilities. According to Pennington, Laughlin, Smithson, Robinson and Boswell (2003), Individual differences in intelligence are seen as differences between people in the rate of processing of simple information. Adapting pedagogy improves teachers' confidence and that of the learners towards their teachers. It also enhances confidence of the community and the parents towards the quality of education offered to their learners.

Substandard performance in secondary schools in Kenya has been attributed to the inability to meet the specific pedagogical strategies to a specific student due to large influx of students in Kenya secondary schools classes which attributed from Free Primary school Education (FPE) that increased the teacher student ratio making it even harder for teachers to meet the immediate learners instructional resource needs. Because of these reason, the government and the Ministry of Education must provide concrete solution to the influx of students in Kenyan secondary schools to ease the teacher burden towards meeting the learners' instructional needs.

8.7 A Critical Analysis on the Impact of Instructional Resources in Secondary Schools in Kenya

At the heart of every teacher is the need to deliver the right content to the learners effectively. Instructional resources play a key role in making instruction process real and lively. Lyons (2012) cited learning as being a complex activity which involves interplay of physical facilities, student motivation teaching resources and skills from the teacher, he also emphasized that teaching and learning resources enhance effectiveness in schools as they bring good academic performance in schools. Choice of instruction resource depends on the ability of a student but the only questions not yet understood is as to how and when a specific instruction resource should be used on a specific student.

New instructional methods are a product of the dynamics in the changing needs of the instruction methods in class. Teachers have a mandate to master the changing instructional process and associate it with the right instruction resource before delivery. Adapting to a new instruction resource is a gradual process which takes time for potential effective class instruction to be achieved and due to this fact; enough support personnel must be given to teachers for them to understand the list of instruction resources to better pedagogy in Kenyan secondary schools.

9. Conclusion

The findings suggest that there has not been adequate preparedness of teachers towards use of instructional resources. There should be a corrective measures aimed at promoting teachers preparedness towards using teaching resources.

There are no enough instructional resources in secondary schools and the ministry of education through the government of Kenya should increase funding aimed at purchase of instructional resources.

The government of Kenya should find an amicable solution to the influx of students in secondary schools in Kenya. This will enable the teachers to meet individual pedagogical needs among students in Kenya secondary school.

10. Recommendation

The study established key areas of pedagogy that need to be reinforced to better teaching and learning in secondary schools in Kenya.

- 1) The Ministry of Education through the Teachers Service Commission (TSC) should develop a comprehensive policy on teacher training towards their preparedness to use instruction resources. Proper and adequate preparedness translates to better class delivery.
- 2) The Kenya Government should increase its funding in the yearly budget to cater for purchase and allocation of instruction resources to secondary schools in Kenya.
- 3) The Non-Governmental Organizations in Kenya to aid developing schools with donations and funds to cater for purchase of instruction resources.
- 4) As the main pedagogical facilitators, teachers should be up the task to acquaint themselves with the latest technology and methodology including the latest instruction resources.

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